

EXPANDED CAREER PROGRESSION SYSTEM: ITS CHALLENGES, PITFALLS AND BENEFITS**Abba M. Raquim**

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ABSTRACT

The Department of Education envisions the total development of its teachers through providing inclusive, practical and consistent professional advancement policies. One of the most recent modifications in the promotional policies of the department was an enactment of Expanded Career Progression System. This study explored teachers' experiences in the implementation of Expanded Career Progression. It was participated by 150 randomly selected teachers across Luzon, Philippines. The study employed phenomenological research design. Results of the study showed that teachers experienced that the implementation of Expanded Career Progression System posed additional workload as it obliges meticulous documentary preparation, difficulty in providing evidences to substantiate teachers' performances and merits. Further, the study concluded that teachers perceived that there were common misconstrued provisions on the policy as they misinterpreted the rules and regulation governing career progression system. Also, teachers experienced that there were lack of proper orientations and lack of consistent discussions pertaining to the valid documents needed to earn substantial points. On one hand, the study also revealed that Expanded Career Progression System offered apparent benefits for professional advancement opportunities as teachers experienced that there were transparent, objective and performance-based promotions since teachers presented their actual and successful accomplishments over the years. The study further recommended the close examination individual teachers' actual experiences in the preparation of documents and actual evaluation processes under the Expanded Career Progression. Hence, the study also recommended to formulate a program intervention that may help teachers to better grasp the implementation of Expanded Career Progression System.

Keywords:

Expanded Career Progression System, teachers, education, promotions, challenges, transparent, objective, performance-based

INTRODUCTION

One of the critical fibers in the achievement of quality education in the Philippines, lies in the competence of teachers. Competence requires substantial skills that put forward effective and efficient instruction. In this line, sharpening teachers' teaching competence is aligned with the very standards mandated by the Department of Education. While, teachers are exerting enormous number of efforts to ensure the effective delivery of basic education among Filipino learners, they are also valued and provided with greater career opportunities that help them develop personally and professionally. Teachers are longing for the competitive salary increase to supplement their basic subsistence. In this regard, when promotions are obtained by teachers through regular processes and procedures in accordance with the department's policies, their ranks and salary grades may also increase. With this, the national government is keen and mindful to help teachers obtain higher ranks depending on their competence and abilities in the teaching profession as they responsibly fulfill their responsibilities and

obligations. The enactment of Executive Order No. 174 s. 2022 otherwise known as the “Establishing the Expanded System of Career Progression for Public School Teachers.” The government continually creates policies that may help teachers obtain better career life by providing sustainable, fair and object metrics of evaluation that directs their potential ranks and government positions. In the resurfacing changes in the educational landscape specifically in internal governance and system of promotions within the department, the introduction and implementation of DepEd Order No. 24 s. 2025 has been subjected to teachers’ scrutiny. This order is otherwise known as the “Expanded Career Progression System for teachers and School Heads in the Department of Education” in the Philippines. This newly promulgated policy within the departments aims to set a systematic and competency-based process of advancement of teachers and school heads along the established career lines in classroom teaching and school administration. Apparently, career progression serves as teachers’ platform for professional development providing them with security of tenure as they are given opportunities for promotions and a sense of professional fulfillment.

The concept of teachers’ career progression in the Philippine undergoes significant evolution. The newly implemented Expanded Career Progression System has shown a strategic shift towards a more structured and professionalized system. In this line, it introduces two distinct career pathways such as the Classroom Teaching (CT) Career Line and the School Administration (SA) Career Line. As contained on Classroom Teaching Career Line, here teachers are primarily involved in classroom instruction encompassing positions from Teacher I to Teacher VII and Master Teacher I up to Master Teacher V. On the other hand, School Administration Career Line is designed for educators who aspire to obtain leadership roles including School Principal I to School Principal IV. Career progression and operational effectiveness are interdependent and essential to organizational performance (De Vera & Martir, 2025). In addition, school heads give career progression due importance however, compensation package is not attractive compared to Public Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and lack of administrative support is observed (Listor, 2024). There is a significant disconnect while foundational policies like the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) and the Expanded Career Progression (ECP) System signify a strategic shift towards structured professionalization (Capistrano & Tamayo, 2025). Further, teachers as government employees potentially sought opportunities as well-defined and properly implemented career progression takes place (Nava-Macali et al., 2019). On the other hand, teachers have demonstrated strong awareness and preparedness across all components of the Expanded Career Progression System (ECPs) specifically on competency-based promotion, position classification, tenure leadership roles and external recognition (Santidad et al., 2025).

The researchers observed that while the intent of the newly mandated promotional policy and position classification in the Department of Education characterizes clear and objective measures of competence of teachers, different experiences of teachers who have posed interests to reclassify their positions based on the competence become a resounding concern with regard to the practical implementation of the ECPs among teachers in Luzon. The researchers further observed that most teachers hold different experiences in line with the implementation of ECPs. In view of these foregoing conditions that the researchers observed, this study explored teachers’ experiences in the implementation of Expanded Career Progression System in the Philippines.

OBJECTIVES

The main objective of the study was to explore teachers’ perceptions in the implementation of Expanded Career Progression System in the Philippines. Specifically, this study aimed to:

1. determine the views and insights of teachers as they prepare for position classification and promotions based on Expanded Career Progression System
2. identify the challenges they encounter as they engaged in Expanded Career Progression containing promotional procedures and processes
3. identify the benefits of Expanded Career Progression System for teachers’ professional advancement

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a phenomenological research design as the study explored teachers’ perceptions in the implementation of Expanded Career Progression System. In addition, the study was participated by 150

randomly selected public school teachers in Luzon. The participants were selected through random sampling technique. Apparently, the researchers used developed guide questions for Focus-Group Discussion. The developed guide questions were arranged using deductive method. Before the actual data gathering, the researchers sought the expertise of professionals to validate the instrument. Experts consisted of Doctorate degree holders in Educational Management and Supervision. In addition, experts expressed “Excellent” remark for each question. This signified that the questions are precise, concise, clear and parallel to the research objectives of the study. Meanwhile, the researcher conducted an actual Focus Group Discussion through Zoom Teleconferencing whereas the researchers provided specific schedules for the administration of the discussion based on the participants’ time availability and convenience. The participants were given a total of 15 minutes to express their perceptions, views and insights relative to the implementation of Expanded Career Progression System. In addition, the participants were informed that their responses would be recorded. Thus, the researcher used thematic analysis through coding-decoding schemes. Application of commonality of responses was used in order to extract participants’ perceptions in the implementation of Expanded Career Progression System. Based from the participants actual responses, the researcher extracted meanings and formulated the major themes and subthemes .

Major Themes	Subthemes
<i>Additional work</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documentary Preparation • Difficulty in Presenting Means of Verification (MOVs)
<i>Misconstruction on Provisions and Rules</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of Proper Orientation • Lack of Consistent Discussions in presenting valid documents
<i>Apparent Benefits</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transparent Processes • Objective Evaluation • Performance-based Promotions

Table 1. Major Themes and Subthemes

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Expanded Career Progression System becomes a strategic shift for teachers’ professional advancement. Public school teachers desired and longing for a consistent, practical and continued career opportunities where they sought to be given wider opportunities for promotions and reclassifications of their positions as government employees under the education department. In this line, there were three (3) major themes extracted. Each major theme reflected subthemes which were based on the actual responses of teachers reflecting their perceptions in line with the implementation of Expanded Career Progression System.

Views and Insights of the Participants. Teachers are vital workforce in the Department of Education as they implement the curriculum and ensure that instructions are effectively discharged. In this line, they view ECPS as an **Additional work**. This serves as the major theme 1 contained two (2) subthemes such as *Documentary Preparation* and *Difficulty in Presenting Means of Verifications (MOVs)*. This shows that participating in promotion or reclassification of their current positions, they viewed that additional work is another burdened which they are to meticulously prepare all substantial documents that can prove their competence in teaching as they seek classroom teaching career line. For them, with the gravity of instructional responsibilities they hold, preparing their documents may also lead to another significant responsibilities. As they desired to obtain the position within the three (3) salary grade limitation. They find it difficult to gather, organize and present all substantial documents proving their performance and competence because there are voluminous workloads and other professional responsibilities tasked to them aside from their personal undertakings. In addition, teachers’ perceived that the implementation of ECPs encompasses rigorous process whereas all Means of Verifications (MOVs) are in line with their primary and other teaching responsibilities including both classroom observable and non-classroom observable performances. They find it challenging to organize and present all of their actions through proper documentation provided that they fulfill different responsibilities simultaneously.

Empathetically, the participants also pointed out that instead of preparing these documents for purposes of promotions and reclassification, they intend to teach and fulfill their basic and primary responsibilities. The findings supported the study of Hakim and Fadillah (2021) which shows that workload has significant effect on employee promotion, work motivation and performance. In addition, similar study reveals that promotion posed another workload for preparation and readiness of employees seeking such promotion. This caused them stress and discouragement to further pursue and join the promotional and reclassification processes. In fact, as articulated by one of the participants:

“I have failed to present substantial MOVs because I have to focus on my primary duty which is to teach. To gather all documents which can reflect my performance and competence require serious amount of time which may hamper the teaching process. So, I really see and viewed ECPS as good policy but needing more time and attention.”

Also, another participant shared that:

“No time to organize my documents and gather them all to ensure my promotion. As a matter of fact, because of my busy schedule for teaching, I find it as my loss since I fail to gather all my documents.”

In addition, one participant made mentioned that:

“I was too stressed in finding and preparing my documents needed, this made really an another work or task for me as a teacher who wanted promotion.”

Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of Expanded Career Progression. Being a newly introduced career progression system as ECPS appears as an evolution of other career progression including promotion and reclassification, there are several challenges encountered by the participants. **Misconstruction on Provisions and Rules** contains two (2) subthemes such as Lack of Proper Orientation and Lack of Consistent Discussions in Presenting Valid Documents. Teachers experienced that they misinterpreted certain provisions on the Expanded Career Progression System Guidelines as contained on the DepEd Order No. 24 s. 2025. Since the policy for career progression is a newly established rules for promotion and reclassification, teachers experienced that they misinterpreted the rules which caused them to present documents which are not necessary or vital to earn points, substantial for their promotion or reclassification. One of the teachers' experiences causing misinterpretation on rules, provisions and processes is the lack of proper orientation. Participants expressed that they received orientations but not quite sufficient for them to comprehensively understand the provisions or guidelines contained thereto. They formally received several orientations focusing on the basic to intricate provisions of the ECPS. However, participants still experienced confusion as to whether the documents they would be submitting and presenting before the panel-evaluators assigned are valid and proper. On one hand, participants also experienced that because there are lack of proper orientations, formal and consistent discussions surrounding the preparation, submission and presentation of valid documents are also lacking. They experienced that they only asked questions to their colleagues and school heads who attended comprehensive discussions pertaining to the current promotional and reclassification system. Based from the participants, the questions they have asked always pertained to the proper and valid documents that can prove their competence and eventually, garner sufficient points for their promotion or reclassification. In addition, participants also experienced that most of the documents they submitted and presented are insufficient thus, contained certain deficiencies. To this effect, they have failed to gather enough points for promotion or reclassification. Presentation of valid and substantial documents becomes a serious challenge of the participants which made them worried about the results of the evaluation. The findings negated the study of Cecchini et al. (2021) which reveals that regulatory orientations and regulatory focus are essential elements to prevent disposition effect among employees. In fact, one of the participants mentioned that:

“I hardly understand the provisions on ECPS because it is a newly implemented policy for promotion which I am not used to.”

As substantiated by another participant:

“I am confused as to how the rules and processes contained in Expanded Career Progression System operates, I think our orientation with regard to that needs to be more comprehensive and it should be continued year round.”

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Benefits of Expanded Career Progression System. While there are challenges and difficulty being experienced by the participants, there are several benefits which Expanded Career Progression System offer. **Apparent Benefits** of the policy includes *Transparent Process, Objective Evaluation* and *Performance-Based Promotions*. The participants experienced that while there are different documentary presentations needed, they experienced that the new promotion and reclassification system provide transparent processes whereas all of aspirants are provided with metrics and dimensions to be measured. Evaluation metrics are based on their primary functions. In other words, the basis needed for promotion and reclassification are based on their roles and responsibilities. In addition, transparent processes also encompass fair and justifiable evaluation system that measure the performances of the participants. Here, participants experienced that their diligence and competence are objectively measured for as long as the documents speak for such performances. Further, participants experienced that objective evaluation takes place, as the system contain clear and precise indicators which serve as the basis for measurement and evaluation of their accomplishments, they are properly guided as to what and how they would be graded. In this line, objective evaluation also shows that evaluators and other personnel-in-charge during the evaluation process are founded with the principle that all teachers are to be evaluated based on the merits of performances rather than employing subjectivity. To this effect, the documents reflecting participants' performances and accomplishments as teachers are comprehensively assessed. Thus, all documents or Means of Verifications (MOVs) reflect the actual performances of teacher-aspirants. The system impliedly presents a valuation on the performances of teachers including classroom-based and non-classroom based performances. In this regard, all actions that positively affected the quality of education which teachers contributed, are highly valued and converted into a more favorable professional advancement. The findings supported the study of Osman and Adanza (2024) which concludes that a well-designed promotion system prioritizing meritocracy, equity and teacher well-being can enhance the teaching force and elevate the education standards. As expressed by one of the participants:

"Before, I am losing hope with my promotion, but now, I am very optimistic and mindful that all of my sacrifices are fairly and objectively acknowledged through fair promotion system."

On the other hand, another participant mentioned that:

"I cannot help myself but to be more hopeful and positive because of the new opportunities provided by the newly implemented system of promotion and reclassification."

Thus, one participant emphasized that:

"I can be now more productive and eager because I know the newly implemented career progression system ensure a performance-based assessment and really the accomplishments of a teacher like me in the teaching field."

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CONCLUSION

Expanded Career Progression System becomes a strategic guide that help public school teachers advance their professional career. This newly implemented system is susceptible for challenges and pitfalls which are normal part of an implemented policy in the government. On the other, it has offered a great advantage for teachers who are aspiring to elevate their professional careers through objective, transparent and performance-based evaluation. The system helped teachers to create more impactful undertakings as they could also benefit from their performances through provision of clear and precise metrics of evaluation substantial to obtain quality instruction leading to the attainment of quality education.

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